

Fostering the Digitalisation of Education through Inter-school Collaborations: A Practical Guide to Building School Networks

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Abstract

This technical report provides a practical guide to create school networks with which to promote digitalisation in education. Building networks is a medium and long-term process, which is facilitated when schools belong to the same institutional context and have a previous history of collaboration. In the initial phases of building a school network it is practical to start with those most active teachers, who are especially motivated in the adoption of digital education. Through different examples, it is shown how networks are started by a small group of educational innovators and then spread to the rest of the teaching staff and to the different schools of the educational community. The key factors in the structure and composition of school networks to facilitate educational digitalization are examined. The report discusses the readiness of both teachers and students to engage in digital education when planning its integration into teaching-learning activities. Visual network representation techniques, such as "Netmap" and "Netmirror", are also presented, which can facilitate awareness and behavioural change among teachers. As a whole, the report presents a detailed guide on how to build networks that can harness the potential of regional and local networks to enable digitalisation of education.

1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This technical report provides a practical guide for fostering digitalisation in education through the creation of inter-school collaborations. Drawing insights from a pilot action-research project in Cantabria, northern Spain, the guide is designed to aid educational decision-makers, both in school leadership roles and policy-making, in creating regional and local networks of schools devoted to enabling digitalisation of education in effective and responsible ways. The report underscores the significance of inter-school networks in supporting capacity building in digital education among teachers and educational organisations. It is in line with the *Digital Education Action Plan (2021-27)*, which highlights that digital technology, when deployed effectively and equitably by educators, can significantly support the agenda of high-quality and inclusive education and training for all learners.

The guide presents a series of practical recommendations, focusing on key aspects that must be carefully considered by educational institutions interested in promoting the creation of inter-school networks. These aspects include whether to build a brand-new network or draw on existing connections, the practicalities of establishing inclusion and exclusion criteria (boundary specifications) in the process of building a network, as well as considerations on the composition networks. In this regard, it argues that the potential of networks is maximised when the schools are part of the same institutional context and have a previous history of collaboration. The report highlights the importance of initiating and maintaining collaboration over time. It recommends bringing together active teachers who are particularly motivated by the adoption of digital education, thus creating an inter-school group of champions that can help motivate colleagues who are less confident in the use of digital technologies in schools. The guide also emphasises the need to give focus to the network. It underlines that a key element of a school's digital plan development is encouraging teachers to collectively reflect on how digital technologies can transform education. Teachers are encouraged to examine the integration of their own personal learning environments with the institutional digital education resources and infrastructures provided by their schools. The report discusses the readiness of both teachers and students to engage in digital education when planning its integration into teaching, learning, and assessment. For an organic consolidation of networks, it suggests initially focusing on building strong inter-school links via institutional leaders and then gradually nurturing the growth of connections between the rest of the teaching staff within and across schools. To improve collaborations and motivation around the digitalisation of educational processes, the report proposes two techniques based on the visualisation of social networks. These techniques, named 'Netmap' and 'Netmirror', create a visual representation of networks that facilitate self-assessment, awareness, and behavioural reinforcement, generating dynamics of social comparison. In conclusion, the report presents a detailed guide on how to build networks that can harness the potential of regional and local networks to enable digitalisation of education.

2. INTRODUCTION

The sharing of expertise through networks and communities of practice is an important way for EU Member States to support capacity building in digital education among teachers and educational organisations; as suggested by the recent *Proposal for a Council Recommendation on the key enabling factors for successful digital education and training* (European Commission, 2023). In particular, collaboration among teachers via across-school and within-school networks has proven to be useful for teacher professional learning and for the development of students' digital competence (Castaño Muñoz et al.).

The *Digital Education Action Plan 2021-27* is grounded on the premise that “Digital technology, when deployed skilfully, equitably and effectively by educators, can fully support the agenda of high quality and inclusive education and training for all learners” (European Commission, 2020, p. 2). In order for this vision to be fulfilled, apart from having access to digital infrastructures and resources, it is essential to ensure that educational organisations have the required expertise to purposively and strategically embed technology-mediated practices in teaching, learning, assessment and all other processes that underpin the delivery of education.

This report presents a guide with a series of practical recommendations proposed with the aim of supporting the creation of regional and local networks of schools specifically devoted to enabling the digitisation of education in effective and responsible ways. This guide is addressed to educational decision makers, both in school leadership roles and policy-making. The recommendations draw on the results from a pilot action-research project (Maya Jariego et al., 2023) in one of the northern regions of Spain: Cantabria. However, the insights are relevant to educational organisations across the EU, given they are based on how educational stakeholders can harness the potential of regional and local networks to enable digitisation of education. The school network guide is in line with the objectives of the *Partnerships for Regional Innovation* (PRI) initiative, which promotes the development of tools and the exchange of good practices between key actors in the green and digital transformations¹.

In Spain, all state-funded schools are legally required² to design their own *Plan Digital de Centro* (Digital School Strategy), as a component of their wider *Proyecto Educativo* (Educational Project). In that process, both primary and secondary education schools are encouraged to base the creation of their digital school strategies on the self-reflection exercise enabled by the SELFIE tool.³ Teachers' digital competence development is one of the main goals of such strategic planning and is defined by the *Marco de Referencia de la Competencia Digital Docente* (INTEF, 2022), which is in turn based on the *European Framework for the Digital Competence of Educators -DigCompEdu* (Redecker et al., 2017) and SELFIEforTEACHERS.⁴

Funded by the Spanish Ministry of Education and Vocational Education and Training (VET) and Next Generation EU Funds, the regional government of Cantabria launched its own regional plan for the Development of Digital Competence in Education (#DeCoDe) with the aim of supporting

¹ See: Bianchi, G., Matti, C., Pontikakis, D., Reimeris, R., Haegeman, K.H., Miedzinski, M., Sillero Illanes, C., Mifsud, S., Sasso, S., Bol, E., Marques Santos, A., Innovation for place-based transformations. ACTIONbook to build partnerships for fair green and digital transitions, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2024, doi:10.2760/561797, JRC135826

² According to the Education Law (Ley Orgánica 3/2020) and the #CompDigEdu programme for the improvement of Digital Education Competence (Programa para la mejora de la competencia digital educativa).

³ <https://education.ec.europa.eu/selfie>

⁴ <https://education.ec.europa.eu/selfie-for-teachers>

280 schools in the planning and delivery of digital education during the academic years 2021-22 and 2022-23.⁵

For this study, two interviews were conducted with each of the 11 research participants (7 female and 4 male), in order to gain insights of their digital education practices and the networks of collaboration in which they are embedded. The study included six public primary schools, three public secondary schools and two "colegios concertados" (privately-owned but publicly-funded primary and secondary schools). The schools were both from rural ($n = 5$) and urban ($n = 6$) areas. All participants were teachers directly involved in the digital transformation of their schools, although they had different roles and responsibilities: namely DeCoDE school coordinators ($n = 5$), ICT coordinators ($n = 4$), members of school leadership teams ($n = 3$).

In this report, we first introduce a number of key aspects that must be carefully considered by any educational institution interested in promoting the creation of interschool networks. In particular, we recommend establishing and formulating networks of schools that are in the same territory, have a previous history of collaboration and are embedded into the same institutional frameworks.

To initiate an inter-school network, we recommend bringing together active teachers who are particularly motivated by the adoption of digital education. This would allow the creation of an inter-school group of champions that can help motivate colleagues who are less confident in the use of digital technologies in schools.

A key element of schools' digital plans development is encouraging teachers to collectively reflect on how digital technologies can transform education while inviting them to examine the integration of their own personal learning environment (PLE) with the institutional digital education resources and infrastructures provided by their schools. The readiness of both teachers and students to engage in digital education when planning its integration into teaching, learning and assessment is a key element, given it would allow teachers and student to examine their progress over time.

For an organic consolidation of networks, we recommend to initially focus attention on building strong inter-school links via institutional leaders and then gradually nurture the growth of connections between the rest of the teaching staff within (i. e. intra-school) and across schools.

In order to improve collaborations and motivation around the digitisation of educational processes, we propose two techniques based on the visualisation of social networks. The annex contains the network visualisations resulting from each interview. This report has been prepared based on the accumulated experience of teachers who were pioneers in the digitization of their educational community. We trust that this experience can be useful in other schools that are facing the digital transformation process.

The guide was used as a reference in the study "Multiple senses of community in adjacent neighbourhoods: an approach based on the analysis of personal networks" (PID2021-126230OB-I00), a "targeted research project" funded by the Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation, which examined community coalitions and education roundtables in Tres Barrios and Polígono Norte, among other neighbourhoods.

⁵ <https://www.educantabria.es/documents/39930/731133/Proyecto+%23DeCoDE.pdf/79ca201d-f8ae-e988-df60-2581677a8838?t=1649843770526>

Improving our knowledge on interschool networks

Teachers need to engage in ongoing learning activities with other colleagues to ensure that their teaching practices remain effective with their students. Among other benefits, professional development programs for teachers offer the opportunity to develop inter-school social capital networks. These networks not only contribute to improving teaching skills, but are also related to job satisfaction and even, under certain circumstances, the performance of their students. Relationships between teachers from different schools increase the diversity of available resources and contribute to generating a sense of belonging to the educational community. In a systematic review of 84 interschool networks, they observed that most of these initiatives were originally established by the educational administration and that they seem functional in obtaining support from other colleagues. However, it is still necessary to determine what works to achieve positive academic results in their students.

Based in: Brown, C., Luzmore, R., O'Donovan, R., Ji, G., & Patnaik, S. (2024). How educational leaders can maximise the social capital benefits of inter-school networks: findings from a systematic review. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 38(1), 213-264.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/IJEM-09-2023-0447>

3. BUILDING THE NETWORK

Networks of schools can be built from scratch or draw on pre-existing relationships. Either way, their boundaries are defined by the membership criteria that specify who is eligible to join them. These two aspects will influence both the composition of the network and its operation. The three aspects are further elaborated in the next sections.

3.1. Establishing brand new links or drawing on existing connections?

The first dilemma when establishing a network is deciding whether to create a network from scratch or take advantage of pre-existing local coalitions in the community. On the one hand, starting the process from scratch gives greater versatility and freedom to the organizational design. However, on the other hand, having some history of collaboration lowers the barriers to participation, since community engagement can be based on already established relationships, values and social climate. The choice between these two alternatives often depends on practical considerations and constraints. Regardless of which one is the chosen approach, it is important to highlight that building networks is a medium or even long-term process.

Suppose we want to create a network of schools to encourage effective and responsible use of digital technologies in teaching-learning processes. We could choose to *create* a brand new network (e.g., “Community of digital practices of the North Region of Spain”) or otherwise build on a pre-existing coalition (i.e., “Townville North District Education Board”) with the aim to redefine its mission and incorporate digital education as a new element into its wider remit. In Table 1 we have compared the possible implications of both alternatives. In the first case, it is very likely that the impetus will come from local or regional authorities (i.e., public bodies responsible for education), which will have to initiate a long-term process. After defining the context of participation, recruitment and motivation of the participants, they will also have to initiate and maintain the collaboration dynamics. In the second case, the necessary conditions for participation already exist and the biggest challenge is to incorporate a new topic of interest among the objectives of an already established entity.

Table 1.

Key differences between creating or leveraging networks.

	Create a network	Leverage an existing network
<i>Process</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Tends to generate top-down dynamics. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Facilitates bottom-up strategy development.
<i>Social distance</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> It entails a greater social distance between the promoters and the participants. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> It can work from personal contacts.
<i>Antecedents</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Starts from scratch. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The previous trajectory and the history of collaboration favour the participation process.
<i>Context</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> It is necessary to create an environment and define the social dynamics to meet and form relationships. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Benefits from the previous structures and social dynamics.

Building a network entails specifying boundaries, recruiting participants, managing incentives, and encouraging collaboration for the intended purposes. Instead, *leveraging a network* entails redirecting existing resources to new aims.

During the data collection of this study, we identified various networks and communities that exemplify how networks can be come into being. In the next box we propose an example of a local network that emerged from the bottom up, at the suggestion of the teachers themselves. By comparison, eTwinning was an initiative promoted by the European Commission (Vuorikari et al., 2011): It is a case that corresponds to a formally promoted network, even though it has the collaboration and active involvement of the teaching staff. Both networks were functional and effective.

An education coalition in the northern district of Seville

The *Polígono Norte* Educational Coalition⁶ brings together schools, social entities, and representatives of public bodies in the northern district of the city of Seville (Spain). In addition to functioning as a space for the exchange of experiences in the educational community, it aims to promote coordination between the different stakeholders involved in the delivery of education in the district, which is one of the most socially disadvantaged metropolitan areas in the south of Europe. State and private schools, non-governmental organizations, local and provincial authorities, neighbourhood entities, families, and students are represented in the network.

The community has existed for 20 years, with the participation of more than 50 entities in the district. Among other areas of intervention, it has focused on preventing school absenteeism, facilitating the exchange of good practices in innovative teaching, encouraging the involvement of families in the educational process of their children, and promoting the interrelation between schools and the surrounding neighbourhoods.

It is a good environment for the promotion of the design of digital school plans by schools. The existence of a prior inter-organizational network facilitates the exchange of experiences between teachers and other members of the educational community. As it has representatives of families and students, both groups are co-participants in the teaching innovation underway. Members can also exchange mutual support throughout the digitalisation of education process. Indeed, the mere existence of the coalition is an indicator of "community readiness" for the change we want to promote in schools in the district. It is a sign of maturity since they are prepared for a specific type of intervention. In other words, the coalition can incorporate the goals of digital transformation within their own remit, rather than creating a new entity for this particular purpose. In this particular case, creating new networks from scratch could conflict with pre-existing local initiatives that are already channelling collaboration between schools and, in doing so, disrupt the ongoing dynamics.

3.2. The boundary specification challenge in network building

In social network analysis, the challenges that normally entail delimiting the set of actors that make up a social system are known as the "boundary specification problem" (Lauman, Marsden

⁶ <https://mesa-de-educacion-del-poligono-norte.jimdosite.com/>

& Prensky, 1983). Some of the most usual strategies to address this issue entail selecting individuals who (a) have certain characteristics in common, (b) engage in social relationships of a specific type, or (c) participate in the same activities. Each strategy has relevant methodological implications.

In parallel, when we *build* networks, the way we define who the members are can also be decisive. Normally, criteria of a territorial, relational, or institutional nature, among others, are used. Each of these alternatives influence the composition and, indirectly, the way the network operates. Each boundary establishes a distinction between the ingroup and the outgroup. Consider, for example, the following cases:

- Schools that are in the same district who share a local context.
- The members of an online forum on digital education that make up a relational community built around a specific topic.
- The schools dependent on the Ministry of Education and Vocational Training of the Government of Cantabria are integrated into a shared institutional and regulatory framework.
- The “Salesian schools” belong to the same organizational environment.
- Even the shared perception of being part of a group of innovative schools implicitly implies a greater potential to establish informal relationships with each other.

The key factors to promote collaboration will be different in each case: personal motivation, shared values, leadership, personal relationships, or organizational hierarchy may act as facilitators to different degrees.

Despite this diversity of factors, when it comes to the educational system, above all other considerations, it is key to use a defined institutional framework. The drive of the government responsible for education in the context of a given school is usually underpinned by a combination of territorial, relational, and institutional factors. Schools operating within the same institutional system and regulatory framework share common aspects and maintain a certain degree of connection with each other. The administration responsible for education in a given jurisdiction has a certain degree of control over the incentives and the normative context that modulate the participation process. All this can facilitate the involvement of schools in a process of collaboration sustained over time.

Classroom, course, and community

In a study with high school students in California, the processes of social influence among adolescents were analysed taking as reference three different ways of delimiting their networks. Namely, researchers traced the networks between (a) students in the same class, (b) the entire grade in their school (which includes different classes) and (c) the wider community. The strongest association between individual use and peer use of tobacco and alcohol was observed at the community level. The empirical relationship was also stronger when friendship relationships were evaluated than when other types of relationships were considered (such as admiration or attribution of popularity, among others). Based on these results, the researchers recommended using the widest possible boundary in network data collection. In addition, the strength of the evaluated relationship is also important in the type of findings that are obtained.

Based in: Valente, T. W., Fujimoto, K., Unger, J. B., Soto, D. W., & Meeker, D. (2013). Variations in network boundary and type: A study of adolescent peer influences. *Social Networks*, 35(3), 309-316.

3.3. The composition of the network

The composition of the network is usually inextricably linked to the previously established boundaries and affects its subsequent functioning. For example, a higher degree of heterogeneity of network members entails management difficulties, but also offers opportunities and diversity. When creating the network, for a selection of schools with whom we want to promote digital transformation, we could encounter the following hypothetical situations:

- A. A group of schools that already have an advanced Digital School Plan in their school. In this case, the exchange between schools could be assimilated to a network of “best practices”, which reinforces the mechanisms for spreading innovation. That is, they can function as a "community of practice" in which they exchange their experience in educational transformation, contributing to a rapid diffusion of strategies that are effective in the development of innovations.
- B. A group of schools with technological infrastructure problems and low levels of digital competence among teachers and students. In this case, the participating schools could offer mutual support or form a coalition aimed at defending common interests and advocating for more resources and support.
- C. A group of schools that differ in the quality of their Internet connection, as well as in how teachers use digital technologies in preparing and delivering lessons, evaluating students, or developing professional relationships with colleagues. In this case, heterogeneity offers opportunities for learning and each school could benefit in a different way from the chance to be in contact with more experienced schools.

When this third alternative is given, it is especially important to determine the optimal way of adding components to the network. In other words, how members join the newly established community). Matching criteria based on the relational characteristics have been found to improve the results of the interventions (Valente et al., 2003): both informal leadership and a formal selection influence processes in natural groups contribute to behavioural change.

Tip 1

To create school networks, we recommend schools and policy makers to select schools that a) have a shared territorial base, b) have previous relationships with each other, and c) belong to the same institutional framework.

4. INITIATING AND MAINTAINING COLLABORATION.

Participation in a group or a network is a long-term process. It usually starts with a small number of particularly active and motivated actors, who have common interests and begin to relate to each other. Little by little, new actors begin to join. Although they are less connected with the group, they develop links with some of the members of the original nucleus. This progressively forms a so called “core-periphery” structure. Understanding this process can help to conceive the network of schools as a social fabric that is gradually being built.

4.1. The formation of a core-periphery structure

In Figure 1, we have represented the collaboration structure between a group of drug addiction prevention professionals. They usually implement educational activities with the collaboration of local schools. The network is organized around a very dense core and a less connected periphery. The actors with the greatest centrality, who are very well connected to each other, are at the centre of the network. That core is surrounded by professionals who have a comparatively secondary role. It can be stated that this network has a “core/periphery” structure.

Figure 1. Collaboration network between community drug prevention professionals. Two different colours indicate the core and the periphery of the network. The core is made up of the 9 most prominent actors. They are the best connected in the network as a whole and are also particularly well connected to each other. Around this nucleus, 36 actors make up the periphery of the network. They are less connected to

each other and to the network, although they are all directly or indirectly connected to the core. Based in Maya-Jariego & Holgado (2021).

In social network analysis, a network is considered to have a core/periphery structure when it is composed of (a) a highly cohesive and interconnected central subgraph and (b) a peripheral subgraph with nodes loosely connected to each other, but with some connections to the core (Borgatti & Everett, 2000). This structure is usually the result of effective participation processes, in which the network grows from the inside out. This occurs as involvement in shared activities spreads from those who are more motivated to those who are less motivated, or from those who are better connected to those who are less connected.

Consider the case of a network of schools that come together to work on the design of their respective digital education action plans. Normally, the first to participate in the process are those teachers who are most active in the use of ICTs in their own teaching practice. This group of pioneers will tend to establish relationships with each other, forming a core of key players in digital innovation. As new participants join, they will do so as less connected teachers, since they are newcomers to the group. In addition, there is a high probability that the original nucleus has a certain power of attraction for the establishment of new links: that is, from the periphery to the centre.

This process runs parallel to carrying out joint activities. For example, when teachers organize a conference on how to design a digital school plan or when ICT coordinators come together to demand that the educational administration facilitates access to a certain Content Management System that is particularly well adapted to their educational context. The results condition the continuity of the participation and of the network that has been initiated. Small initial achievements reinforce and encourage persistence in the pursuit of the objectives and create strong bonds within the nucleus of the group. In addition, as teachers gain shared experiences and develop relationships of mutual help, a greater commitment to participation to the network of schools is generated.

Community coalitions as interorganizational networks

A community coalition is a group of organizations working together to achieve a common goal. A paradigmatic case is the network of hospitals, health centres, non-governmental organizations and entities involved in public health services that was launched in Wisconsin to reduce infant mortality in the black minority in the state capital. The interorganizational network improved coordination and was highly effective in reducing health disparities with the white majority. More specifically, the longitudinal analysis of the network of participating entities showed (a) a significant increase in the density of the network over time, and (b) the prominent role of some organizations that acted as leaders, facilitating the establishment of contacts between third parties. Both the density and the existence of intermediaries were important in improving services and, consequently, in reducing infant mortality.

Based in: Faust, V., Christens, B. D., Sparks, S. M., & Hilgendorf, A. E. (2015). Exploring relationships among organizational capacity, collaboration, and network change. *Psychosocial Intervention, 24*(3), 125-131.

4.2. Maintaining engagement over time.

A "driving group" is key in the initial phases of the participation process. **When such a group exercises effective leadership, it is more likely to entice new participants to join in at later stages. Thus, usually "success doesn't lie in a handful of digital enthusiasts"⁷, but it is necessary to maintain motivation over time and progressively increase the participation base.**

Small achievements are very important in the beginning. Any initial reinforcement provides an impetus to continue. Personal relationships and shared experiences are then developed in the group and contribute to maintaining participation. In addition, when this continues over time, the participants develop a greater commitment to the organization, to the network of schools or to the community initiative with which they are involved. Eventually, engagement shapes the identity of participants and the probability of abandonment is reduced, since individuals acquire greater resilience in the face of all kinds of obstacles and stronger bonds. This combination of motivation, commitment and identity can lead to participation becoming a self-sustaining process.

Tip 2

To start a network of schools, it is important to bring together in the initial phases a small selection of educational establishments (or representatives of the educational community), from among the most active and motivated, so that they establish contacts with each other, that will allow them to create a "driving group".

⁷ Allen Crawford Thomas and Mark Ayton. "How to shape your digital strategy. How to create a broad, organisationally-focused digital strategy that develops digital capabilities and harnesses the potential of digital devices and services.", 26 January 2021, <https://www.jisc.ac.uk/guides/how-to-shape-your-digital-strategy>

5. GIVING A FOCUS TO THE NETWORK

The formation of schools network usually revolves around a topic of common interest. In our case, the goal is to foster the integration of digital tools in educational contexts. In this regard, it is relevant to examine (a) how to incorporate digital resources into the teaching-learning processes realising their maximum potential, and (b) how to combine teachers' personal learning environments effectively and responsibly with the digital platforms and devices offered by the educational institution. We focus on both topics below.

5.1. Four levels of digitalisation of education

The SAMR model establishes four levels of change in relation to the use of digital technologies within teaching-learning process in the classroom, namely: Substitution, Augmentation, Modification, and Redefinition (Puentedura, 2013). As represented in Figure 2, it is a continuum from the lowest to the highest degree of impact of digitalisation on the educational process (Romrell, Kidder & Wood, 2014).

Figure 2. *The SAMR model.* © Lefflerd via Wikimedia Commons, CC BY-SA.

We can illustrate it with an example:

1. *Substitution.* A teacher distributes additional readings to her students through an open source online learning platform provided by her school. Instead of resorting to photocopies, she shares PDF files. However, the teaching-learning dynamic remains the same. In this case, technology only fulfils a substitution role, with no functional changes.
2. *Augmentation.* In this case, the teacher distributes an enriched PDF, with links to interactive content. Thus, students have access to videos and photographs that illustrate the educational content, and they can do self-assessment quizzes. On this occasion, in addition to the digital substitution, there has been a functional improvement.

3. *Modification*. In addition to distributing an enriched PDF, the teacher uses an online tool with which students can collaboratively underline and share the text fragments that they have considered most important in their reading. In this case, there is a significant redesign of the task, since the students generate a collective product in which the contents that the group considers most relevant are prioritized. This also allows them to compare and discuss the main ideas of the reading.
4. *Redefinition*. Students not only underline the text during class, but they also use a messaging app to discuss with peers as they read. They also have access to an online forum in which they resolve doubts, recommend similar readings that they find while reading or reflect on the social implications of what they read. Throughout the different sessions, the readings are organized in a shared repository, with a collaborative tagging system. Students collaborate with each other during the learning process. This is the creation of a new task associated with reading.

According to the SAMR model, the first two levels represent an improvement in the teaching-learning process, thanks to technology. However, the last two levels go further as they also entail a transformation of the teaching-learning process.

This model can be useful to guide the work of a school network: the participants can reflect on how to incorporate technology in the classroom in such a way that it enables and possibly transforms teaching activities. It is not so much a question of assuming that "more technology equals more learning", but of reflecting on how to integrate and appropriate technology in the classroom in such a way that it contributes to the teaching and learning process and takes advantage of its full potential to promote collaboration.

5.2. On the intersection of Personal Learning Environments and Institutional Digital Education Ecosystems

In their daily teaching practice, educators rely on a range of digital resources, information systems, and communication technologies provided by their schools and/or relevant authorities (e. g. ministries of education). They can be regarded as "institutional" because they are officially supported or approved, regardless of whether they are maintained by in-house ICT technicians and infrastructures (e. g. own servers and software installations) or are otherwise contracted from service providers.

At the same time, teachers frequently comment that they often complement such an institutional digital education ecosystem with other elements of their own personal learning environments (PLE), making use of their own devices (e. g. smartphones) as well as third-party platforms they find useful. PLEs refer to the highly diverse and comprehensive socio-material entanglements that each individual mobilises to learn, including people, technologies, information, places and institutions. Beyond individual's cognition, development and behaviour, PLEs address learning as a situated, sociocultural and lifelong phenomenon, while paying particular attention to the technologies that mediate learners' meaning-making processes and the contexts in which such technologies are used (Dabbagh and Castaneda, 2020). Therefore, institutional digital education ecosystems are embedded into the wider PLEs of both educators and students.

We have depicted such overlap between institutional and personal resources in Figure 3.

Figure 3. A student's personal learning environment encompasses institutional and non-institutional resources.

The combination of digital tools provided by educational institutions with the PLEs of educators (and students) can decisively influence the learning outcomes resulting from technology-mediated educational processes. That is why it is necessary to think strategically about how to integrate them effectively and responsibly into teaching-learning processes. In this regard, interoperability and interconnection are key (Conde et al., 2014), but also adopting a critical lens that goes well beyond functionality in order to make sure that the ethical and pedagogical implications of technology adoption are thoroughly considered (Castañeda & Villar-Onrubia, 2023).

We can illustrate this by means of the example presented in Figure 4. It shows the PLE of a university professor, which includes elements from her institutional digital education ecosystem as well as online services and platforms available from third-party providers. In this case the "learning management system" available at her university is *Blackboard*, a proprietary platform contracted from an established corporation in the EdTech sector. A substantial part of the teaching and learning, including the distribution of educational materials and the interaction with the students, are channelled through this platform. The professor also uses the services of the "virtual secretary" as well as the electronic resources provided by the library. In addition, her day-to-day academic, administrative, and professional communication rely on the use of her institutional email address. These are the most used institutional electronic resources within her PLE.

However, the same professor also uses other online tools in her daily work, which are available from third-party providers and have not been necessarily endorsed or approved by her university. She has a blog on *WordPress.com*, where she publishes teaching notes and disseminates her own research work. She uses a microblogging platform (Twitter) to spread news about her field of expertise and, in doing so, nurture her online professional network. She also communicates frequently through a messaging app (WhatsApp) with her research group, and through a social media platform (Facebook) with former students. Last, she uses the services of very large online platform and search engine provider (Google) to find academic literature and to translate texts that she uses in her teaching.

Figure 4. *Personal learning environment and institutional digital education ecosystem of a university professor.* The online services officially provided by the university are located within the triangle. The digital resources outside the triangle are accessed from third-party providers. Source: Own elaboration, based on Lanclos, D. M., & Phipps, L. (2019).

Likewise, students also tend to build hybrid PLEs in which institutionally provided resources and tools are supplemented with third-party technologies, which have not been necessarily approved, or even evaluated, by either their institution or teachers.

On the one hand, institutional digital infrastructures can enhance consistency in the learning experiences of all students, help schools and educators meet their duties (e. g. with regard to data protection and information security or accessibility), and ensure technical support. On the other hand, the external tools (i. e. those beyond institutional services) that students choose to integrate into their PLE allow them to address their own preferences or needs in a more tailored

way while embedding learning into their everyday digital practices. The interoperability between formal and informal contexts improves the relevance of educational actions and facilitates the transfer of knowledge to natural contexts. The effective coexistence of both requires some kind of interconnection.

However, it is essential for both educators and students to critically evaluate the platforms and tools not supported by their institutions that they would like to adopt in their teaching and learning practices, so that they can make an informed decision on the opportunities and risks they might bring with them. This is important for legal, ethical and practical reasons, as “free” platforms operated by third parties often rely on the extraction and monetization of personal data.

As we have seen in this section, the interplay between institutional and personal digital resources is highly important and cannot be ignored by educational stakeholders concerned with the effective and equitable adoption of technology education. Therefore, in order to maximise opportunities for positive impact, school networks should address both dimensions of EdTech.

5.3. Designing a digital school plan

A digital school plan is an instrument that aims to promote the use of digital media both in teaching-learning processes and in school management. According to the *European Framework for Digitally Competent Organizations* (Kampylis et al., 2015), the plan is expected to address the impact of digitalisation in seven different areas, namely: infrastructure, leadership and governance, teaching and learning, professional development, assessment, content and curriculum, as well as support and collaboration networks (INTEF, 2020)⁸. The SELFIE tool was designed to help schools self-evaluate their digital capacity in each of these sections.

For each of these dimensions, schools should carry out a situation analysis and define the goals guiding their own plan. The type of contents that can be addressed are illustrated below.

Table 2.

Areas for designing the digital school plan.

	Contents
<i>Infrastructure</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technological equipment of the centre (e. g. connectivity, devices), both for teaching in the classroom and general administrative management.
<i>Leadership and governance</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Existence of a digital strategy in the school, use of technologies to promote the participation of teachers, students, and other interested parties; and implementation of digital resources to facilitate decision-making.
<i>Teaching and learning</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of digital platforms for teaching in the classroom or at a distance and use of digital resources to transform the teaching-learning process.
<i>Professional development</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promotion of digital competencies of teachers, and efficient integration of personal and organizational learning environments.

⁸ To do this the SELFIE self-assessment tool can be used: <https://education.ec.europa.eu/selfie>

<i>Assessment</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of digital technologies in student assessment, including self-assessment, peer assessment, and documentation of one's own learning.
<i>Content and curriculum</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creation of digital content by teachers and students, with proper use of open licenses and other indicators of digital literacy.
<i>Support and collaboration networks</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exchange of information and support between members of the educational community, inside and outside the school (including school networks).

Adapted from: INTEF (2020). *Plan digital de centro. Descripción y guía*. Madrid, Ministerio de Educación y Formación Profesional.

These areas can be used as a guide in the development of teachers' personal networks, or social networks in the school as a whole. In each of them, teachers (or schools) could count on specialized support resources. That is, individuals or organizations that cover such area of need, providing support or information.

The communication between the different members of the educational community (parents, students, managers and teachers) has a central role, whatever the medium chosen for interaction (Rondan-Cataluña, Peral-Peral & Ramírez-Correa, 2023).

5.4. Eight areas for reflection

SELFIE is a self-reflection tool with which schools can identify their strengths and weaknesses in the use of technology, based on the views of all key stakeholder groups in their communities. Through the anonymous participation of students, teachers and school leaders, data are gathered around eight different areas: leadership; infrastructure and equipment; collaboration and networking; professional development; teaching support; teaching pedagogy; assessment practices; and digital competence of students (see Figure 5). The tool has shown good psychometric properties (Costa, Castaño-Muñoz & Kampylis, 2021), but the sections have been updated since this assessment. This collective assessment serves to detect the needs of each school based on different stakeholder needs (school leaders, teachers and students), reflect on how to promote the effective and responsible use of technology, and design the digital school plan. It also allows detecting when there is a discrepancy in the point of view of the different stakeholders, given the tool could be used to stimulate discuss and participation of students, teachers and school staff as a whole.

Figure 5. Eight dimensions in the SELFIE tool.

Tip 3

In developing the school's digital plan, teachers can reflect on (a) how to use digital technologies to transform the educational process and (b) how to integrate personal learning environments with the digital resources of the school. It is also of interest that they self-assess the functionality of their personal networks for each of the eight areas identified with the SELFIE tool.

6. DESIGNING FOR TECHNOLOGY-MEDIATED LEARNING

Digital devices, such as computers and smartphones including the software they contain, may adopt multiple forms and are continuously updated (Mishra, Koehler, & Kereluik, 2009). They have the potential to enable different actions and practices, as the same device might be used for numerous purposes; including multimodal communication, accessing content (e. g. to read, watch, listen), producing content (e. g. text, multimedia), interacting with people and systems (e. g. gaming, following social media accounts), etc. Digital technologies have now pervaded all aspects of contemporary society and, by becoming ubiquitous, they have blurred the lines that used to keep apart some activities, places and social worlds from others.

Over the last four decades, technology-mediated teaching and learning have proliferated across all levels of education and extended far beyond the realm of distance education. Those educational practices in which technology operates as “the means by which information is conveyed and people are linked together” (Bower, 2019: 1036) have resulted in both new opportunities and challenges. While technology has been approached too often as a ‘silver bullet’, expected to easily fix educational problems alone, reality is far more complex (Robins and Webster 1989). Indeed, “the past 40 years has shown that even the most extensively implemented educational technology innovations have mixed and inconsistent outcomes” (Facer & Selwyn 2021: 4).

Outcomes are heavily influenced by the actions, competences, motivations and beliefs of multiple actors (e. g. students, teachers, families, and the educational administration) and the social contexts in which they are embedded. This makes the very notion of ‘best practice’ contentious for neglecting context and its crucial role in shaping institutional and individual choices (Bayne et al. 2020). A key aspect of educators’ professional practice is what can be described as *design for learning*: “the process by which [they] arrive at a plan or structure or designed artefact for a learning situation [...] as small as a single task, or as large as a degree course” (Beetham & Sharpe, 2020:6). In other words, they envision a sequence of actions to be performed by students with the aspiration of helping them achieve the intended learning outcomes as defined in the curriculum. Likewise, educators usually create and select different kinds of resources (e. g. content, tools) that students need in order to perform those actions, while others are given by the institutional and wider social context in which learning takes place. Even though digital tools are essential in technology-mediated teaching and learning process, their autonomy as drivers of educational enhancement is only limited as they always operate in conjunction with other factors that are equally important (Timotheou et al., 2023). Goodyear et al. (2021) identify four kinds of ‘designable’ components that influence the activity of students and actual learning outcomes resulting from it: (a) the tasks that students are expected to complete and knowledge on which to draw, (b) the physical resources and contexts for learning (e. g. tools, artefacts, spaces), (c) the proposed social interactions (e. g. groupings, roles), and (d) the intended learning outcomes.

6.1. Readiness for educational uses of digital technology

Readiness for the adoption of digital technologies in education depends on factors such as (a) the awareness of their relevance, (b) the skills of teachers and students, (c) their previous experience and exposure to initiatives aimed at promoting its integration into the classroom, or (d) the existence of a context of dissemination and exchange of these experiences within the framework of a network of schools.

In Table 3 we list three levels in the preparation for the use of digital technologies in the classroom and relate it to the SAMR model levels presented in chapter 3. In each case, we indicate some strategies that can support the integration of technology in the classroom and, therefore, help articulate the work of networks of collaboration established for that purpose.

- **Level 1:** At the initial levels, there is hardly a significant use of digital technologies in the classroom. There is little awareness of its relevance and there are hardly any examples of its integration into the classroom. In this case, inspiring cases and examples and actions aimed at raising awareness are especially effective. In some cases, this could mean that schools where very little technology is integrated are invited to visit other schools where technology is highly integrated in an effective way.
- **Level 2:** At the intermediate levels, we find sporadic use of digital technologies, mainly focused on improving the teaching and learning process, rather than on its transformation. In this case, it is necessary to foster participation in the exchange networks of the largest possible number of teachers and schools. Likewise, promoting leadership and creating coalitions can be an effective strategy. For example, establishing local groups at schools to work collaboratively on the design of their digital plans or promoting that schools from different educational districts collaborate and provide mutual support in the adoption of digital technologies.
- **Level 3:** When the use of digital technologies is widely widespread, the challenge is to maintain the new practices sustainable in time so that they become mainstream. It is also useful to collect evidence on the effectiveness of such educational practices through systematic evaluation, as well as systematize examples of practices. Thus, knowledge based on previous experiences is consolidated, while contributing to its standardization and dissemination.

What follows from these three levels is that the promotion of educational digitisation within a network must be tailored to the starting situation of each school. Raising awareness, creating networks or systematising practice are, respectively, the three most relevant actions based on the degree of prior preparation of the educational context.

Table 3.

Levels of preparation and types of use of digital technologies in schools.

Levels	Strategies	Expected uses (SAMR model)
Level 1. <i>Lack of, or very limited, digital education expertise and/or infrastructures</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conducting self-reflection exercise based on the views of students, teachers, and school leaders on how technology is used in their school (SELFIE). 	NONE SUBSTITUTION
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ignorance of the needs related to digital technologies. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Encouraging teachers to reflect on how they are using digital technologies in their professional practice (SELFIEforTEACHERS). 	

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identification of competence and resources gaps as well as any other need for effective and responsible delivery of and participation in digital education. • Provision of information and basic training in response to the identified needs. and associated pedagogies • Evaluation of existing digital needs and resources in the school. • Awareness on educational needs related to digital technology. 	
<p>Level 2. <i>Initiation to the use of digital technologies</i> but no institutional planning on digital education</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Changes begin at school. • Access to basic digital education infrastructures and resources • First experiences of use. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promotion of leadership in the use of digital technologies. • Identification of successful cases of digital education • Sharing of expertise • Development of working groups for the elaboration of digital school plans. • Use of SELFIE to shape the design of digital school plans and training plans. • Encouraging the use of SELFIEforTEACHERS to inform the professional development of each teacher. • Professional development opportunities in relation to digital education 	<p>SUBSTITUTION AUGMENTATION</p>
<p>Level 3. <i>Institutionalization and professionalization of digital education.</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digital school plans approved. • Experiences of digital transformation. • Continuous support of public administration and other educational agents. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development and dissemination of successful digital education practices. • Support for existing experiences, to facilitate maintenance. • Systematization of the practice of integration of digital technologies in the classroom. • Use of SELFIE for the monitoring of digital education development • Encouraging use of SELFIEforTEACHERS to inform continuing professional development 	<p>MODIFICATION REDEFINITION</p>

6.2. Levels of use of digital technologies in schools.

Different teaching and learning tasks can be associated with different levels of technology use. To promote the acquisition of knowledge, the substitution and augmentation levels described

above may be sufficient. However, to promote the development of competencies, modification or redefinition levels are most often required. At each level, the role of the teacher is different, the tasks required, and the competencies displayed are also different (Priyadi & Basuki, 2021).

At a substitution level, the teacher's role is primarily that of an *instructor* and is primarily concerned with students' acquisition of the ability to collect and summarize information. For example, a teacher can instruct students to use a tool like OpenStreetMap to locate a geographic location instead of using a physical atlas. Or they may use word processing tools to produce papers and reports. In this case, the objective is simply to instruct to replace an analog tool with a digital one. Students acquire knowledge by searching and summarising information, relying on the digital tools that enable this task.

At the "augmentation" level, the objective of using digital technologies is to enrich the information obtained, so that it contains resources that would not be possible without these tools. In this case, the teacher acts primarily as a *facilitator* of the learning process, although he still exercises significant control over achievement standards. For example, students can be taught to use OpenStreetMap to measure distances between two places or to calculate routes to follow. Or they can use thesauruses or grammar checks to improve text writing or enrich documents with hyperlinks and audiovisual resources. In this case, students have gone from simply collecting information to giving added value to this information, including resources that modify the way it is presented and facilitate its access.

Digital technologies can be used to redesign the tasks that students are required to complete, so that they improve their ability to adapt resources to their learning needs. This integration can occur in contexts where students have greater autonomy and the teacher acts as a *motivator* or guide for their learning. For example, students can use predefined layers or create their own personalized maps with OpenStreetMap using uMap, in order to geolocate resources or relate geographic variables and social realities. Likewise, online tools can be used to do collaborative work, in which each group member can adopt different roles (content producer, reviewer). Although there may be broad standards and pre-established learning objectives, the results of this type of strategy are not always as expected and may lead to unexpected learning and even informal learning.

Finally, digital technologies can be inserted in open environments, where students act as agents of their own learning objectives and collaborate in defining their own teaching space. Using the same example, students can create narrated tours of a specific location and generate products such as guides to places around them. They can even respond to demands for social and health services in their community to create maps or tools to detect needs in the local population. They could use generative Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools as an assistant for the synthesis or drafting of texts that help in the preparation of these works or as support for the creation of essays or reports, through the logical ordering of the proposals that arise through brainstorming that they can then share and discuss with the rest of the class. In this case, the teacher acts as an inspiration for ideas or courses of action that the students then develop using tools they might already use in their leisure or tools that the teachers direct them to. Or even simply as a mediator between the demands of the environment and the learning needs of the students.

Table 4.

Levels of use of digital technologies and relationship with the teaching and learning process in the classroom.

Level of use	Teacher role	Tasks	Context of interaction
<i>Substitution</i>	Instructor	Summarize and gather information	Offline
<i>Augmentation</i>	Facilitator	Add and enrich information	Mainly offline Online individual work
<i>Modification</i>	Motivator	Adapt and adjust resources to learning needs	Mainly online
<i>Redefinition</i>	Inspirator	Creation of learning spaces and content updating.	Online

In short, the use of digital tools must be adjusted to the type of teacher-student relationship, the ISCED level of students and the learning approach used in the classroom. In this sense, the transformative use of digital technologies requires pedagogical processes that go beyond mere instruction and provide students with tools to create content and gain autonomy in their own learning process. These considerations are important for the configuration of teacher networks and should therefore inform the design of their activity. Educational networks work best when they take into account the level of preparation of the participating teachers and when they anticipate the characteristics of the students they are targeting.

Tip 4

To integrate digital technologies in the classroom, it is convenient to consider the level of prior awareness of teachers and the degree of preparation of students. The effective use of technologies in education requires close alignment with intended learning outcomes and systematic evaluation of its effectiveness in reaching such outcomes.

7. STRUCTURE AND COMPOSITION OF PROFESSIONAL NETWORKS IN EDUCATION

In their day-to-day practice, teachers always rely on a personal network of contacts within their immediate professional environment. Those networks are primarily integrated by colleagues, at their own school and other centres, but they may also include other kinds of actors. In the case of primary and secondary school teachers, professional networks normally consist of a heterogeneous group made up of co-workers at their own school, teachers at other schools, learning technologists, training and professional development providers, vendors (e.g. publishers, EdTech corporations), as well as officials from one or more administrations with responsibilities in the field of education (e. g. national, regional and local governments). When it comes specifically to the effective and responsible adoption of technology-mediated educational practices, interpersonal resources play a prominent role. In order to unpack the influence of such networks in educational processes, we will look at how these resources are organized at both individual and institutional level.

7.1. Individual level.

Figure 6 represents the personal networks of two teachers who, in addition to their teaching responsibilities, hold the position of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) coordinator at their respective state schools. This example illustrates the existence of individual differences in the formation of personal networks, even in the case of professionals who have similar duties and are in the same regulatory contexts.

The network of ICT coordinator A (left) contains two-thirds of contacts who also work as teachers at the same school, making for a highly cohesive subgroup (n = 20, 66.6%). The rest of his contacts come from the regional education administration (n = 7, 23.3%), the teachers training centre (n = 2, 6.6%) and a university (n = 1, 3.33%). Therefore, his personal network consists of two clearly defined subgroups.

The network of ICT coordinator B (right) constitutes a single highly cohesive group. Interestingly, his usual contacts are shared between the school where he works (n = 10, 33.33%) and a second school (n = 13, 43.33%). Members of the educational administration (n = 4, 13.33%) and the teacher training centre (n = 3, 10%) also appear.

These two networks could reflect two different professional development strategies. In one case, the activity of the ICT coordinator is mainly focused on the school itself, while in the other case the ICT coordinator seems to find alternative resources in professional colleagues from other centres. **A priori, the first could enable the consistent implementation of activities in a group with a cohesive climate. The second could facilitate and have access to new information and, consequently, the adoption of innovative practices.**

On the other hand, the structure of the network can also have practical implications. Perhaps the network with two cohesive subgroups (on the left) reflects the hierarchical structure from schools to educational administration (bottom up). On the other hand, a network with high connectivity (as in the example on the right), could facilitate the integrated operation of the different roles that comprise it (that is, teachers, administration officials, technicians, etc.). Each network represents a different scenario for the introduction of innovative digital practices in teaching activity.

Such visualizations, together with other qualitative data collected during interviews, allow the researcher to create a narrative and give a more precise interpretation of the network. We will see it in the next chapter.

The personal networks of the digital pioneers in the schools of Cantabria

In a study with the schools of Cantabria, in the north of Spain, we observed three different profiles among ICT coordinators in schools: (a) a part of the coordinators distribute their professional contacts between the school in which they work and the staff of the regional government or the teacher training centre: it is an institutionalized profile, which largely develops the digital policies established by the educational public administration; (b) a second group has more heterogeneous personal networks, with many contacts with teachers from other schools: they normally have an innovative profile and act as promoters of digital transformation in the educational community; and (c) a third group concentrates their relationships in the school where they teach: in consequence, by participating in a network of schools, they could benefit from access to new resources and new information. These three profiles are represented in the Annex to this guide, with a summary of 11 schools that provided information on the exchange networks in which they participate and the digital tools they use in their teaching practice.

Based in: Maya-Jariego, I., Holgado, D., Santolaya, F. J., Villar-Onrubia, D., Cachia, R., Herrero, C. & Giannoutsou, N. (2023). Teachers' personal networks reveal two types of pioneers in educational digitalization: formal and informal intermediaries. *Computers and Education Open*, 4, 100137. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.caeo.2023.100137>

7.2. Institutional level

Each teacher uses a specific combination of tools, in their teaching practice, in their coordination with co-workers and in their relationship with families. Some of these tools depend on the decisions that the teacher makes individually, while others are driven by the educational system. For example, it is common for the teacher to find a virtual teaching platform that is used in all schools in the region. It is also usually the educational administration that decides the work environment, which can result in the predominance of the Microsoft system, the Google toolkit, or a free software environment.

This scenario has relevant implications for building a network of schools:

1. **Public administration** is a central actor in the design of the sociotechnical system of schools, so it should be taken into consideration in the construction of collaboration networks between teachers. In addition to institutional support, they determine the technological endowment, regulate the development of the digital capacities of the teaching staff and administer the incentives to participate.
2. The **ICT coordinators act as intermediaries** between the public administration and their educational establishments. This makes them key figures in the digital transformation in their educational establishments. At the same time, they operate as springboards to initiate collaboration, due to their ability to structure the entire educational community.
3. Consequently, collaborative networks are often deployed in two consecutive steps. First, they connect the key actors from different schools with each other. Secondly, the networks are expanded in each educational establishment, through the progressive involvement of a greater number of actors.
4. Effective ICT coordinators have a dual role. On the one hand, they act as **interfaces for each school with the network of centres. On the other hand, they act as promoters of digitalisation in their own centre.**

Tip 5

It is useful to start the formation of the network through contacts between centres, before encouraging the growth of the network within each centre. The creation of a nucleus between schools (with leaders connected to each other) sustains the subsequent diffusion among the rest of the teaching staff.

Figure 6. *Two personal networks of teachers in their teaching practice.* The colours represent the role of the members of the personal network: blue = teachers from the same school as the respondent; coral pink = teachers from other schools; light blue = officials of the Department of Education; yellow = teacher training centre; green = university researchers. The size of each node represents betweenness centrality, that is, the number of shortest paths that pass through said node, which therefore reflects its ability to intermediate between different spaces or groups. (Maya-Jariego et al., 2023).

8. VISUALIZING NETWORKS FOR INTERVENTION.

Network analysis and visualization can be used as an intervention strategy. Thus, they serve both to diagnose the state of collaboration between schools and to monitor the development and evolution of the network. In addition, the visual representation facilitates reflection and awareness and contributes to dynamizing participation. Accordingly, we present two techniques that are useful in the creation of networks around the digitalisation of education.

8.1. Tracing a network as a group.

The first technique consists of proposing to a group of teachers that they indicate (a) the key actors for the creation of a network of digital schools in a specific geographical environment, (b) the degree of power and influence of each one of them, and (c) how they are related to each other and what groupings already exist. It is about developing a sociogram in a shared way, in which the participants agree on the relevant institutions and people, as well as on the structure of relationships between them. This generates a shared diagnosis and facilitates the development of strategic plans. Based on an evaluation of the starting situation, in sociogram format, the participants can make decisions about the best way to promote the digitalisation of education. They can also reflect, for example, on leadership, the existence of factions or the need to establish bridges that facilitate communication. In Box 1 we have illustrated the type of questions that can be used to apply the *Netmap* technique.

Box 1. Questions to apply the *Netmap* technique.

NETMAP approach [*Consensual and participatory elaboration of a sociogram of relevant actors in the digitalisation of the school*]

In this session we are interested in commenting on the people and organizations that are relevant to you, as an educational establishment, in the digitalisation process.

Layout of the network according to a consensus process – evaluation

1. First, can you please list people and entities that are relevant to the digitalisation of your centre?
2. Which actors are more relevant? Which actors have more capacity to influence others?
3. Can you indicate which actors (individuals or organizations) are related to each other?

Debate on the network characteristics and strategies to follow for digitalisation

4. Now that we can visualize the network we have mapped out, which actors are particularly well connected? What factions and groups can be identified in the network?
5. Considering the structure of the network, what things should we take into account when designing a digital school plan? What should we modify or improve for a good educational digitalisation process?

A networked vision of SELFIE areas

6. Finally, we would like to discuss the people and entities that are relevant for each of the following areas regarding digital education:
 - a. Leadership
 - b. Collaboration and Networking
 - c. Infrastructure and Equipment
 - d. Continuing Professional Development
 - e. Pedagogy: Support and Resources
 - f. Pedagogy: Implementation in the classroom
 - g. Assessment Practices
 - h. Student Digital Competence

Participatory diagnosis with the network of digital pioneers in the schools of Cantabria

In the aforementioned study with the schools of Cantabria, the participants identified a list of key actors in which the following were represented, among others: the school management team, the ICT coordinator, the counsellor, the teachers' centre, the co-workers at school, students and families.

From this list of actors, different resources are activated depending on the initiative they intend to develop. For example, to promote digitalisation, the regional Ministry of Education, the school management team and the ICT coordinator are key actors. To design the Digital School Plan, a collaboration is established between the management team and the teaching staff. While in the SELFIE project the teachers, the management team and the Ministry of Education collaborate. And so on.

The teachers considered it necessary to have a permanent seminar for ICT coordinators, in which to exchange experiences. For this it is important that it is a stable and institutionalized group, which also has a good information management system.

Based in: Maya-Jariego, I., Holgado, D., Santolaya, F. J., Villar-Onrubia, D., Cachia, R., Herrero, C. & Giannoutsou, N. (2023). Teachers' personal networks reveal two types of pioneers in educational digitalization: formal and informal intermediaries. *Computers and Education Open*, 4, 100137. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.caeo.2023.100137>

8.2. Interpreting networks data

The second technique consists of presenting teachers with the graphic representation of a network from which the data has previously been obtained. In this case the teachers participate in the interpretation of the network. The visual presentation of networks often conveys information that informants are not intuitively aware of. This allows them to reflect on their interpersonal environment and become aware of the social structure that surrounds them. On the other hand, the perception of collaboration networks does not usually leave them indifferent, but rather generates behavioural changes. Thus, the register and/or visualization of the interaction becomes a reinforcer and can trigger processes of social comparison. That is why graphic representation can be used to improve collaboration, increase participation, or promote group dynamics. In box 2 we have illustrated the type of questions that can be used to apply the *Netmirror* technique.

Box 2. Questions to apply the *Netmirror* technique.

NETMIRROR approach [*Anonymized presentation of the personal networks obtained in the previous phase*]

In this session we are interested in commenting on the people and organizations that are relevant to you, as an educational establishment, in the digitalisation process.

Presentation of the personal networks gathered during the previous phase

1. From the visualization of the personal networks, can you please mention which are the main people and entities that are relevant to the digitalisation of your centre?
2. Based on the visualization of the personal networks, which actors are more relevant? Which actors have more capacity to influence others?
3. Based on the visualization of the personal networks, which actors are particularly well connected? What factions and groups can be identified in the personal networks?
4. Considering the structure of the personal networks, what things should we consider when designing a digital school plan? What should we modify or improve for a successful digitalisation of education?

A networked vision of SELFIE areas

5. Finally, we would like to discuss the people and entities that are relevant for each of the following areas regarding digital education:
 - a. Leadership
 - b. Collaboration and Networking
 - c. Infrastructure and Equipment
 - d. Continuing Professional Development
 - e. Pedagogy: Support and Resources
 - f. Pedagogy: Implementation in the classroom
 - g. Assessment Practices
 - h. Student Digital Competence

Raising awareness of the risk of HIV infection through the visualization of sexual contact networks

AIDS prevalence in Kenya is 6.7 percent for the population as a whole and more than 20 percent for the Luo people. Polygamy, and in general having concurrent sexual partners, generates a risk of contagion through indirect exposure and especially increases dissemination, as it more likely coincides with the acute phase of HIV infection.

A preventive intervention based on network visualization was carried out in several Luo villages. First, through visual representations of the networks of sexual contacts, the

differences in the transmission of the disease were shown, comparing when there are multiple serial partners or when they are concurrent. Second, it also empirically illustrated how small changes in the prevalence of concurrency can lead to very large changes in network connectivity. The intervention facilitated risk awareness and prompted community discussion on how to reduce risky sexual practices.

Based in: Knopf, A., Agot, K., Sidle, J., Naanyu, V., & Morris, M. (2014). "This is the medicine:" A Kenyan community responds to a sexual concurrency reduction intervention. *Social Science & Medicine*, 108, 175-184.

Tip 6

The visual representation of networks can be used to improve collaboration between schools, since the observation of networks between teachers or between schools (a) facilitates self-assessment and awareness, (b) works as a behavioural reinforcement, and (c) generates dynamics of social comparison.

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9. CONCLUSION

Teachers exchange information, support, and technical assistance in the process of digital transformation of their educational practice. These exchanges contribute to the development of the digital capacity of the schools of which they are a part. In this document we have shown that the construction of school networks makes it possible to formalize the interaction that occurs between teachers and, therefore, they become a facilitator of sociotechnical innovation in educational organizations.

In order for the school networks to work effectively, it is recommended that the participating schools belong to the same territorial and institutional area. On the other hand, participation is a long-term process in which the persistence and involvement of the most active teachers is needed. Connecting pioneers from different schools often works very well, as it brings the educational community together as a whole, creates a positive social norm, and accelerates the diffusion of innovations.

In developing the school's digital school plan, teachers need to reflect on how to integrate digital technologies to transform the educational process. This normally requires adaptation to the specific context of the school and the type of relationship between students and teachers in that context. Visualization and participatory strategies facilitate building networks.

Here are some of the key ideas we've introduced throughout the guide:

- Collaboration between schools drives educational innovation and digitalization.
- When creating school networks, it is necessary to consider the political and institutional context of the educational community.
- When starting a network of schools, it is important to connect the key players with each other.
- The persistence of participation over time is fundamental in obtaining results.
- Digitalization not only consists of substituting some technological means for others, but also carries enormous potential for transforming educational practices.
- SELFIE has demonstrated the importance of critical reflection by the educational community itself on its degree of preparation for digitalization.
- The analysis and visualization of relational data can boost the participation of teachers in experiences of teaching innovation and digital transformation.

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11. ANNEX.

Network development and use of digital tools: Case study of 11 schools in Cantabria.

School 1

- Secondary school (Town with less than 10.000 inhabitants).
- Coordinator of DeCoDE program (Duration of the interview: 181 minutes).

WhatsApp Facebook Additio Idoceo

The coordinator's personal network is concentrated in his secondary school: more than three quarters are colleagues from his own school.

The coordinator of the DeCoDE program has a personal website where he uploads all the contents of his subject openly. This makes it easier for him to teach and, together with the students, allows accessing and interacting with other colleagues from different schools.

This high school relies fundamentally on Microsoft tools, which it combines with the centre's website and other complementary apps. Teachers do not have in-depth knowledge of the tools they use. This leads them to duplicate usage, with other apps. New platforms emerge continuously, so continuous training is necessary.

Note. *Left:* The colours represent the role of the members of the personal network: blue = teachers from the same school as the respondent; coral pink = teachers from other schools; light blue = officials of the Department of Education; yellow = teacher training centre; green = university researchers and trainee students. The size of each node represents betweenness centrality. *Centre:* The triangle is based on: M. Lanclos, Donna, and Lawrie Phipps. '13. Leadership and Social Media: Challenges and Opportunities'. In *Social Media in Higher Education: Case Studies, Reflections and Analysis*, edited by Chris Rowell, 141–50. OBP Collection. Cambridge: Open Book Publishers, 2020. <http://books.openedition.org/obp/8671>. *Right:* Representation of how platforms are connected because they have common users.

School 2

- Primary school (Town with less than 10.000 inhabitants).
- ICT coordinator (Duration of the interview: 184 minutes).

WordWorld Kahoot Genially Youtube Google Search Facebook Yedra

Two-thirds of the respondent's personal network is from the school where he works. However, he also maintains regular contacts with the staff of the Regional Ministry of Education and with two members of the Teacher Training Centre. The most relevant people that act as intermediaries in the network are the school management team and some members of the public administration.

Staff generational change was the starting point for a new plan for the school, which is now committed to digital transformation in the medium term. The school started using Google Suite for Education. After the pandemic, Microsoft applications have been provided and promoted by the Regional Ministry of Education. Now the school aims at combining both. It also has some specific tool licenses for the creation of educational content.

The workload and lack of time make it difficult to learn and incorporate new digital practices in daily teaching. In addition, there are great differences in the digital skills of teachers: some are quite competent and others very little. As seen in the graph, in this case the respondent uses both Microsoft and Google in the school.

Note. *Left:* The colours represent the role of the members of the personal network: blue = teachers from the same school as the respondent; coral pink = teachers from other schools; light blue = officials of the Department of Education; yellow = teacher training centre; green = university researchers and trainee students. The size of each node represents betweenness centrality. *Centre:* The triangle is based on: M. Lanclos, Donna, and Lawrie Phipps. '13. Leadership and Social Media: Challenges and Opportunities'. In *Social Media in Higher Education: Case Studies, Reflections and Analysis*, edited by Chris Rowell, 141–50. OBP Collection. Cambridge: Open Book Publishers, 2020. <http://books.openedition.org/obp/8671>. *Right:* Representation of how platforms are connected because they have common users.

School 3

- Primary school (Town with less than 10.000 inhabitants).
- Head of studies (Duration of the interview: 160 minutes).

It is a network with a fairly heterogeneous and balanced composition. The Head of Studies has contacts in the school where she works, but also in other schools. Informal contact with other centres allows her to obtain information about digital tools, as well as find a solution for some of the difficulties that may arise. These relationships are often informal, based on teachers' personal contacts and needs.

It is a centre located in a rural context, although in recent years it has been transformed into an area of families that work in the capital. In the last 10 years, the population as well as the number of students at the centre have grown considerably. It is a centre located in a rural context, although in recent years it has been transformed into an area of families that work in the capital. In the last 10 years, the population and the number of students at the centre have grown considerably. A few years ago, they participated in the Samsung Smart School project, which has improved the provision of equipment and digital skills.

The Ministry of Education through European Funds has consolidated the centre's infrastructure. The SELFIE tool was used as a diagnostic strategy before designing the school's digital school plan. Currently they organize everything around OneDrive and rely on Yedra for teacher monitoring.

Note. *Left:* The colours represent the role of the members of the personal network: blue = teachers from the same school as the respondent; coral pink = teachers from other schools; light blue = officials of the Department of Education; yellow = teacher training centre; green = university researchers and trainee students. The size of each node represents betweenness centrality. *Centre:* The triangle is based on: M. Lanclos, Donna, and Lawrie Phipps. '13. Leadership and Social Media: Challenges and Opportunities'. In *Social Media in Higher Education: Case Studies, Reflections and Analysis*, edited by Chris Rowell, 141–50. OBP Collection. Cambridge: Open Book Publishers, 2020. <http://books.openedition.org/obp/8671>. *Right:* Representation of how platforms are connected because they have common users.

School 4

- High school (Urban area, more than 50.000 inhabitants).
- DeCoDE coordinator (Duration of the interview: 154 minutes).

This is a highly cohesive school. It is one of the smallest schools in Cantabria, located in a rural village with very little population. The management team has been stable at the school for about fifteen years. The professional contacts of the DeCoDE coordinator are practically reduced to his own educational establishment. There are only two teachers from other high schools.

The centre is considered well-equipped with ICT infrastructures. The challenge is to get teachers to incorporate the available devices into daily teaching. The Microsoft Teams platform is used, which is complemented by WhatsApp and other tools for occasional use. The school provides one tablet per student.

Yedra is the platform around which teaching activities are organized in Cantabria. The existence of multiple channels sometimes makes the information exchanged redundant. Teachers are concerned that technological devices are a distraction for students. There is a generational gap among teachers in their availability to use digital technologies. Older teachers close to retirement are more reluctant to invest in the required training.

Note. *Left:* The colours represent the role of the members of the personal network: blue = teachers from the same school as the respondent; coral pink = teachers from other schools; light blue = officials of the Department of Education; yellow = teacher training centre; green = university researchers and trainee students. The size of each node represents betweenness centrality. *Centre:* The triangle is based on: M. Lanclos, Donna, and Lawrie Phipps. '13. Leadership and Social Media: Challenges and Opportunities'. In *Social Media in Higher Education: Case Studies, Reflections and Analysis*, edited by Chris Rowell, 141–50. OBP Collection. Cambridge: Open Book Publishers, 2020. <http://books.openedition.org/obp/8671>. *Right:* Representation of how platforms are connected because they have common users.

School 5

- Primary school (Town with less than 10.000 inhabitants).
- DeCoDE coordinator (Duration of the interview: 107 minutes).

Except for four people, most of the members of this personal network are from outside the school where the teacher works. In part it corresponds to the profile of a professional who has previously worked in other schools. In this specific case, this is important because it is an area of social exclusion, in which access to external resources becomes an opportunity.

The school is located in a context of social exclusion, with Roma and immigrant families. The school is well equipped technologically: each teacher has a laptop, and each student has access to a tablet in the classroom. Even though some teachers have acted as promoters of technological innovation, its use in the classroom by different teachers is uneven. The digital practices revolve around Office 365, along with some complementary open-source tools. For example, ClassDojo is used to keep in touch with families and Snappet is used as teacher support for content.

In this case, WhatsApp, email, and Instagram are mainly used as resources for informal coordination between teachers from different centers.

Note. *Left:* The colours represent the role of the members of the personal network: blue = teachers from the same school as the respondent; coral pink = teachers from other schools; light blue = officials of the Department of Education; yellow = teacher training centre; green = university researchers and trainee students. The size of each node represents betweenness centrality. *Centre:* The triangle is based on: M. Lanclos, Donna, and Lawrie Phipps. '13. Leadership and Social Media: Challenges and Opportunities'. In *Social Media in Higher Education: Case Studies, Reflections and Analysis*, edited by Chris Rowell, 141–50. OBP Collection. Cambridge: Open Book Publishers, 2020. <http://books.openedition.org/obp/8671>. *Right:* Representation of how platforms are connected because they have common users.

School 6

- “Colegio concertado” privately-owned but state-funded school (Town with less than 10.000 inhabitants).
- School principal (Duration of the interview: 149 minutes).

This is a personal network focused on the school in which the respondent is principal, with specific contacts with the staff of the Regional Ministry of Education and with other schools' principals.

This is a school in the fishing district of Santander, with a high percentage of immigrant population. It is a small school with a well-coordinated small number of teachers. Several years ago, they started working with the Google toolkit (GSuite), but after the signing of the agreement between the government of Cantabria and Microsoft they have made a transition to the Office 365 tools ecosystem, provided free of charge by the regional government. They complain that Microsoft's system doesn't work well with mobile devices.

Privately-owned but state-funded schools have not had access to the provision of devices for public centres. They use Teams as the virtual learning environment. They continue to use GSuite for some tasks (e. g. video storage), but very occasionally. The Ministry of Education only provides support in relation to the use of Microsoft tools (which is covered by European data protection legislation). The school has contracted a specific tool to channel communication with families, while for accessing digital educational content, they have also a license with Aula Planeta Digital.

Note. *Left:* The colours represent the role of the members of the personal network: blue = teachers from the same school as the respondent; coral pink = teachers from other schools; light blue = officials of the Department of Education; yellow = teacher training centre; green = university researchers and trainee students. The size of each node represents betweenness centrality. *Centre:* The triangle is based on: M. Lanclos, Donna, and Lawrie Phipps. '13. Leadership and Social Media: Challenges and Opportunities'. In *Social Media in Higher Education: Case Studies, Reflections and Analysis*, edited by Chris Rowell, 141–50. OBP Collection. Cambridge: Open Book Publishers, 2020. <http://books.openedition.org/obp/8671>. *Right:* Representation of how platforms are connected because they have common users.

School 7

- Primary school (Medium-sized city, between 10,000 and 50,000 inhabitants).
- ICT coordinator (Duration of the interview: 182 minutes).

In this personal network, few colleagues from the school where the respondent works appear in her personal network (7 in total), but she is mostly open to outside resources. Especially she relates to teachers from other schools, advisers that give information on digital educational practices, and university researchers. This allows her to exercise the role of dynamizing the school, providing innovative resources to teachers and students.

In this school, students have tablets in the first years and from the fourth year there are 25 chromebooks per level. They also have a virtual classroom per class. They have organized the web portal as a learning space. Each course has its own blog. Now they use Teams because Office 365 is the one provided by the Ministry. They want to redefine blogs as personal learning spaces.

The ICT coordinator plays the role of animator. She accompanies her colleagues in the use of ICTs and dynamizes the centre. One of the limitations of Teams is that it is not well suited to younger children. In this case, email and mobile phones are used to sustain the network of contacts between teachers.

Note. *Left:* The colours represent the role of the members of the personal network: blue = teachers from the same school as the respondent; coral pink = teachers from other schools; light blue = officials of the Department of Education; yellow = teacher training centre; green = university researchers and trainee students. The size of each node represents betweenness centrality. *Centre:* The triangle is based on: M. Lanclos, Donna, and Lawrie Phipps. '13. Leadership and Social Media: Challenges and Opportunities'. In *Social Media in Higher Education: Case Studies, Reflections and Analysis*, edited by Chris Rowell, 141–50. OBP Collection. Cambridge: Open Book Publishers, 2020. <http://books.openedition.org/obp/8671>. *Right:* Representation of how platforms are connected because they have common users.

School 8

- Primary school (Urban area, more than 50.000 inhabitants).
- School principal (Duration of the interview: 133 minutes).

The personal network of the school director is concentrated in the school she manages, with occasional connections with the Teacher Training Centre and an information technology advisor. Although she is very connected with the teaching staff, she says she finds some attitudes that are not very open to continuous training and some resistance to the incorporation of ICTs in the classroom from her staff.

All activity, both teaching and communication with families, is channelled through the Microsoft platform. It is also used in the organization of teaching teams and work with students, mainly through Teams. They are currently making a compilation of open educational resources to create virtual learning environments.

The school is in a middle-class neighbourhood on the outskirts of Santander. They initiated a digital school plan, following the regional ministry of education established it as a priority. Now there is sufficient technological equipment and there is an effort to connect it with European directives. They point out that there are so many platforms that there is not time to become familiar with all the resources. They also consider that greater involvement of families is necessary.

Note. *Left:* The colors represent the role of the members of the personal network: blue = teachers from the same school as the respondent; coral pink = teachers from other schools; light blue = officials of the Department of Education; yellow = teacher training center; green = university researchers and trainee students. The size of each node represents betweenness centrality. *Center:* The triangle is based on: M. Lanclos, Donna, and Lawrie Phipps. '13. Leadership and Social Media: Challenges and Opportunities'. In *Social Media in Higher Education: Case Studies, Reflections and Analysis*, edited by Chris Rowell, 141–50. OBP Collection. Cambridge: Open Book Publishers, 2020. <http://books.openedition.org/obp/8671>. *Right:* Representation of how platforms are connected because they have common users.

School 9

- “Colegio concertado” privately-owned but state-funded school (Urban area, more than 50.000 inhabitants).
- Deputy director and ICT coordinator (Duration of the interview: 120 minutes).

The deputy principal of the school has a highly cohesive personal network, concentrated almost exclusively in the school where she works. She also has a contact with an official from the Cantabria Ministry of Education.

It is a small private school with public funding. It was created to serve the population in a situation of social exclusion, which includes both the Roma population and the immigrant population residing in the neighbourhood. Families do not always have cell phones to facilitate the connection of students. The regional ministry of education has enabled Microsoft and Office accounts. The centre has old resources and some of the teaching staff also find it difficult to adapt to the new applications.

Classroom computers have Windows XP installed, so many teachers bring their own laptops to work. The computer room has 15 newer computers, with the Windows 10 operating system. Students work with canvas and do programming activities. Most of the time these computers are used by high school students. Programming is currently being taught from the first year of secondary education.

Note. *Left:* The colours represent the role of the members of the personal network: blue = teachers from the same school as the respondent; coral pink = teachers from other schools; light blue = officials of the Department of Education; yellow = teacher training centre; green = university researchers and trainee students. The size of each node represents betweenness centrality. *Centre:* The triangle is based on: M. Lanclos, Donna, and Lawrie Phipps. ‘13. Leadership and Social Media: Challenges and Opportunities’. In *Social Media in Higher Education: Case Studies, Reflections and Analysis*, edited by Chris Rowell, 141–50. OBP Collection. Cambridge: Open Book Publishers, 2020. <http://books.openedition.org/obp/8671>. *Right:* Representation of how platforms are connected because they have common users.

School 10

- High school (Medium-sized city, between 10,000 and 50,000 inhabitants).
- ICT coordinator (Duration of the interview: 147 minutes).

This is a personal network eminently centred on the school, but in which there are also external contacts with ICT experts from the administration or the teacher training centre. These are advice resources and informative support that are very practical in the digitalisation process.

The centre is in a dormitory town, close to the capital. It has grown in recent years and has a lot of interim staff. Each teacher has a computer, and the centre also provides it to families if they need it. A digital plan has been started, but it is still in its infancy and the workload makes it difficult to develop it in depth.

The pandemic was a boost for the incorporation of digital tools. Teachers coordinate through Teams. Students should log into Teams daily, in case there are homework assignments. The regional ministry of education's push for Microsoft tools has led some teachers to resign from Google. The ICT coordinator spends a large part of her time maintaining equipment.

Note. *Left:* The colours represent the role of the members of the personal network: blue = teachers from the same school as the respondent; coral pink = teachers from other schools; light blue = officials of the Department of Education; yellow = teacher training centre; green = university researchers and trainee students. The size of each node represents betweenness centrality. *Centre:* The triangle is based on: M. Lanclos, Donna, and Lawrie Phipps. '13. Leadership and Social Media: Challenges and Opportunities'. In *Social Media in Higher Education: Case Studies, Reflections and Analysis*, edited by Chris Rowell, 141–50. OBP Collection. Cambridge: Open Book Publishers, 2020. <http://books.openedition.org/obp/8671>. *Right:* Representation of how platforms are connected because they have common users.

School 11

- Primary school (Town with less than 10.000 inhabitants).
- Member of the team to promote digitalization (Duration of the interview: 85 minutes).

She has approximately two-thirds of her usual professional contacts within the school and one-third outside. Most of her contacts at school are with other teachers. Outside of school, she is in contact with technicians, ICT coordinators and other colleagues who participate in the development of the digital plan in their respective centres.

It is a small centre, in a clearly rural environment. The school never had a stable, quality internet connection, until last year. Not even the official virtual platform (Yedra) worked well. Now the centre is well endowed and can afford digital educational innovations. Among other difficulties, they mention lack of time, work overload and the reactive attitude of part of the teaching staff to incorporate this type of innovation.

Now the centre is based on the Microsoft digital ecosystem (Teams, Office, Onedrive), and its use is common in the classroom by both teachers and students. Attempting to use Matific, Snappet, and Genially has also been brought back. This has made it especially pertinent to reflect on digital skills and initiate the digital school plan.

Note. *Left:* The colours represent the role of the members of the personal network: blue = teachers from the same school as the respondent; coral pink = teachers from other schools; light blue = officials of the Department of Education; yellow = teacher training centre; green = university researchers and trainee students. The size of each node represents betweenness centrality. *Centre:* The triangle is based on: M. Lanclos, Donna, and Lawrie Phipps. '13. Leadership and Social Media: Challenges and Opportunities'. In *Social Media in Higher Education: Case Studies, Reflections and Analysis*, edited by Chris Rowell, 141–50. OBP Collection. Cambridge: Open Book Publishers, 2020. <http://books.openedition.org/obp/8671>. *Right:* Representation of how platforms are connected because they have common users.